

CHARACTERISTICS OF ANXIETY DISORDERS (REACTIVE AND PERSONAL ANXIETY) IN PATIENTS WITH SPINAL TUBERCULOSIS

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ABSTRACT

Studying anxiety levels is of great clinical importance, as psychoemotional factors influence the course of the disease, quality of life, and the effectiveness of therapy. The Spielberg-Khanin Anxiety Scale is one of the most reliable methods for quantifying anxiety as a state (reactive) and as a stable personality trait

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Objective: To study the characteristics of the level of reactive and personal anxiety in patients with spinal tuberculosis, and to determine their relationship with clinical and social factors.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted from 2016 to 2023 at the Bukhara Regional Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Phthiology and Pulmonology, involving 98 patients with spinal tuberculosis. Of these, 45 (45.9%) were men and 53 (54.1%) were women aged 20 to 76 years (mean age 49.9 ± 13.5 years). The control group consisted of 20 apparently healthy individuals, including 18 women and 2 men aged 21 to 53 years.

Among the examined patients (50%) were not working at the time of the study, 29.6% were pensioners, 6.1% were disabled, and only 14.3% were employed.

To determine anxiety levels, the Spielberg-Khanin Anxiety Scale (Yu. L. Khanin, 1976) was used. It includes 40 items: 20 to assess situational (reactive) anxiety and 20 to assess trait anxiety. The results were interpreted as follows:

- up to 30 points – low level of anxiety,
- 31–45 — moderate,
- 46–60 — high.
- 61 and above – very high.

Results: According to the study results, the majority of patients exhibited high levels of both reactive and trait anxiety. Among patients with complicated spinal tuberculosis, high levels of reactive anxiety were observed in 28.8% of those examined, while very high levels were observed in 48.1%. Rates of trait anxiety were similar: 30.7% of patients had high levels, while 36.5% had very high levels. In the control group, moderate levels of anxiety predominated (70%), indicating the psychoemotional stability of healthy individuals. A direct correlation was established between anxiety levels, disease severity, and patients' social status.

A χ^2 analysis ($\chi^2 = 43.72$; $df = 6$; $p = 0.000000084$) revealed statistically significant differences in anxiety levels between the study groups. Patients with complicated tuberculous spondylitis were significantly more likely to experience high and very high levels of anxiety, reflecting severe emotional stress and depletion of the body's adaptive capacity.

Patients with limited spinal tuberculosis exhibit moderate anxiety levels, while the majority of those in the control (healthy) group exhibited low to moderate anxiety levels. These data indicate a direct correlation between the severity of the tuberculosis process and the severity of psychoemotional disturbances.

In patients with complicated spondylitis, high anxiety levels were observed in 28.8%, and very high anxiety levels were observed in 48.1%. In patients with limited forms of tuberculosis, these figures were 30.4% and 34.8%, respectively. In the control group (healthy individuals), the average anxiety level was predominant—70%.

Thus, the degree of expression of reactive anxiety is directly related to the severity of the pathological process and reflects psychoemotional stress caused by physical suffering and social maladjustment.

Conclusion: Patients with spinal tuberculosis exhibit elevated levels of reactive and personal anxiety, manifesting in psychoemotional stress and decreased adaptive capacity. High anxiety levels reduce treatment effectiveness and indicate the need to include psychological support in a comprehensive rehabilitation system. The findings confirm the need to incorporate psychological correction and psychotherapeutic support into a comprehensive rehabilitation system for patients with spinal tuberculosis. The Spielberg-Khanin Scale is a reliable and informative tool for assessing psychoemotional status and monitoring treatment progress.

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